

Time Organ: Precision, Imperceptibility, and Synchronization of Quantified Time

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Abstract

From the earliest mechanical water clocks, humans have divided time into calculable units through tools, continuously seeking the most precise frequencies in nature to measure time more accurately. Advancements in technology have led to the emergence of the concept of “attosecond,” a unit of time down to seventeen decimal places. However, even with such minute divisions, this increasingly precise measurement of time has become disconnected from human’s most direct bodily experiences, letting the relationship between time and bodily sensation insensible. “Time Organ” project investigates this “insensible” of human sensory time. Through virtual reality, heart rate sensing, and custom-built water-dripping mechanical devices, it creates multi-sensory experiential situations. Based on scientifically quantified time and bodily frequencies, the project generates sensory experiences from asynchronous to synchronous, encompassing visual, auditory, and tactile sensations. Inspired by the concept of extending organs, the project aims to create a tool for perceiving the passage of bodily time. By using human’s innate synchronicity and sensory extensions, it seeks to rediscover the perception of bodily time, thereby realigning human’s temporal sensations with their bodily frequencies.

Keywords

Bodily time, Quantified time, Entrainment, Synchronization

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1 Introduction

Humans have been exploring the relationship with time since the variations of sunrise and sunset. In 2023, the Nobel Prize in Physics was awarded to Pierre Agostini, Ferenc Krausz, and Anne L’Huillier for their research on attosecond optical pulses [6]. “Attosecond,” as the smallest international unit of time currently known, not only provides a new tool for human research in electronic physics but also verifies capability to utilize time variations down to seventeen decimal places.

The pursuit of more precision and more quantification in units of time is reflected in various aspects of life. For instance, in the third century BCE, Ctesibius (285 BCE - 222 BCE) invented the mechanical water clock, which enhanced the precision of timekeeping devices through mechanical design and initiated the division of time into precise units. From then until now, whether through the oscillation of crystals or the frequency generated by electronic transitions, the development of timekeeping devices aims to further subdivide time. The improvement in the precision of timekeeping devices has a significant impact on modern technological development, extending to various fields’ applications in subdividing time. For instance, imaging technology have advanced, and movie has allowed to shoot at 120 frames per second (fps) today. However, such advanced development has not been widely adopted. This is because the range of differences perceivable in human vision is around 60 fps. Excessively high frame rates can lead to jarring visual experiences and discomfort for viewers due to the lack of visual motion blur, which the human eye naturally accommodates. Considering this, when we pursue in utilizing smaller units of time how many aligns with our bodily sensations? And how many precise units of time are simply imperceptible to our bodies without the aid of instruments? “Time Organ” art project attempts to explore the sensations of bodily time by designing a system that combines virtual reality with mechanical devices.

2 Infinite Precision and Bodily Insensitivity

Philosopher Henri Bergson once used spatialization to explain that humans build scientifically quantified time through the presentation and variations of objects in space. He also contrasted unit-based time with the continuous sensory time perceived by the body [1]. Despite the conceptual difference between quantified time and bodily time, people still tend to adhere to quantification and uniformity and most things are expressed in quantifiable terms nowadays. However, when these quantified units are at scales beyond what the human body can directly perceive or distinguish, our understanding of time gradually shifts from “human sensation” to “unit representation.” We entrust our own sensations to these units, leading to an increasing insensibility of our own sense of time.

3 Reclaim Sensation— Synchronization

The body has its own time, but it is generally seldom noticed. Quantified thinking accustomed us to precise scientific time, gradually causing us to lose our most direct bodily sensations and making the relationship between time and bodily experience imperceptible. However, is it possible for the perception experiences beyond

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consciousness be altered through mechanisms of perception manipulation? The rubber hand illusion [3] demonstrates that cross-modal synchronized experiences can create illusions even if people can feel their bodies through sensory neurons. In these experiments, the brain of the experienter links the visual perception of a fake rubber hand being struck with their own tactile sensation of pain, altering their direct bodily sensations through synchronizing touch and vision. Another related experiment is the out-of-body experiment [5]. In this experiment, the experienter wears a VR headset to view footage filmed from directly behind themselves. This creates the illusion of leaving their body, as the visual input matches the tactile sensations they experience. Such experiments have also been applied in artistic creation. “Outrospectre” (Frank Kolkman, 2016) [4], designed a virtual reality based on the out-of-body experiment, creating illusions through the synchronization of visual and tactile senses. This artwork attempts to help people confront their fear of death by simulating a near-death experience, demonstrating how the synchronization of multimodal perception can alter an individual’s body perception. In addition to the synchronized sensory stimuli generated externally in the experiments mentioned above, humans have an inherent tendency toward synchronization, known as “entrainment,” where individuals naturally align with environmental harmony, enhancing or prolonging phenomena. Given that synchronization can alter bodily sensations, it raises the question: how can we use synchronization to make people aware of their most intuitive perception of time?

4 Research Method: Multi-sensory Experiment

Based on the aforementioned theory, we propose the following hypothesis: “Synchronization can prompt individuals to perceive time with bodily rhythms.” We designed the following multi-sensory experiment framework, modeled after the rubber hand illusion. In the rubber hand illusion, tactile and visual synchronization shifts the perception of the limb from the real hand to a fake rubber hand. In our study, we aim to transfer the time perception from familiar quantified time to bodily time through tactile and visual synchronization. Furthermore, by referencing the use of multi-sensory cues in the “Outrospectre” project to enhance participants’ perception of synchronization, we incorporated auditory elements into our experiment to achieve a more diverse sensory synchronization experience. Below is our experimental procedure:

- **Research Background:** People’s perception of time has gradually shifted towards quantified time rather than bodily perception. The aforementioned experiments, including the Rubber Hand Illusion and Out-of-Body Experiences, are related to sensory synchronization that influence participants’ bodily perception. They investigate how synchronizing various sensory inputs can alter bodily perceptions. In particular, Out-of-Body Experiments can even modify bodily ownership and spatial awareness [2]. Given these findings, we attempt to explore whether sensory synchronization can also influence time perception.
- **Hypothesis:** Synchronization can prompt individuals to perceive time with bodily rhythms.
- **Experimental Method:**
 - (1) Participants wear VR and tactile simulation devices.

- (2) The device detects the participant’s heart rate and provides tactile feedback.
- (3) The visual and auditory stimuli in the VR synchronize with the tactile feedback.

- **Verification of Hypothesis:** Determine whether multi-sensory synchronization truly affects heart rate and participants’ perception of time.

Rubber Hand Illusion

Transfer of Limbs (Pain)

Time Organ

Transfer of Time Perception

Figure 1: Comparison of experimental procedures between Time Organ and rubber hand illusion (Provided by Chi-Hung HUANG).

5 Time Organ: Exploring Bodily Sensation of Time

In the context of the above, “Time Organ” tries to rediscover the direct bodily sensation of time through art and experiment. In this project, our primary research objective is to explore whether we can stimulate the body to return to the most direct perception of time through synchronization. Based on cross-modal synchronization experiments, “Time Organ” designs a system that combines virtual reality with mechanical dripping devices, correlating “seconds” with “heart rate” to investigate the interplay between these two frequencies. In addition to exploring the reasons for the loss of sensation, it aims to guide people’s perception of time towards synchronization with bodily frequencies through this artwork.

5.1 Interactive Mechanism:

- (1) The experienter begins by sitting down and wearing a virtual reality (VR) helmet and guided to place their hands on the dripping device.
- (2) The sensor on the dripping device starts detecting the experienter’s heart rate and converts it into dripping rate.
- (3) The visuals and sound in the VR change based on the quantified time “seconds” as the frequency.
- (4) After a period, as the experienter becomes accustomed to the frequency of quantified time, the speed of visual and auditory changes gradually to the heart rate and the water start dropping and guiding the perception of time towards bodily frequencies.

Figure 2: Interactive mechanism explanation diagram for Time Organ (Provided by Chi-Hung HUANG).

5.2 Design Principles

The artwork is divided into two parts: the “Heart Rate Drip-ping Device” and the “Virtual Reality.” Here are detailed explanations for each:

- **Heart Rate Dripping Device:** The design of the dripping device is based on the concept of “extension organs of the human body,” akin to medical equipment. In addition, references the earliest mechanical water clocks, the device employs water as a tool for perceiving changes in time. Different from traditional time measurement, the water in the artwork is used to let experiencers perceive the passage of bodily time. In exploring the direct bodily sensation of time, this project use “bodily frequencies” to represents the flow of bodily time. The human body has various frequencies with different scales, such as brainwave, blinking, breathing, sleep cycle. To establish synchronization, the artwork selects two frequencies with similar scales from bodily frequencies and quantified time: “heart rate” and “seconds.” (The average heart rate for most people ranges from 60 to 80 beats per minute, which is close to the duration of one second). When the experiencer put the hand on device, the water will be dropping onto the palm according to heart rate. The sensation of water dripping amplifies the bodily sensation of the heart rate.
- **Virtual Reality:** At the begin of the experience, the experiencer will sense different time frequencies in both visual and tactile sensations. Within the VR, visual elements include light, water, numbers, etc., are changing according to the frequency corresponding to seconds. And there is a narration speaking a story about the development of time-keeping tools. Guided by narration, the experiencer will gradually experience synchronization of touch, vision, and hearing over approximately five minutes. This experience guides individuals to perceive time in alignment with their bodily frequencies.

5.3 Device Design

- **Heart Rate Sensing:** The device in this project utilizes the Polar Verity Sense optical heart rate sensor, known for its Bluetooth wireless realtime communication, water-proof feature, and the ability to detect heart rate simply by

Figure 3: Time Organ dripping device and virtual reality experience. Video recording of works: <https://youtu.be/JDbawHteUw?si=sMkJevjjeoz-DT> (Provided by Chun-Huang LIN).

Figure 4: In virtual reality, the audience interacts with virtual water droplets(Provided by Chun-Huang LIN).

resting on the skin of the up-per arm. This minimizes the inconvenience of wearing additional devices for the audience and addresses hygiene concerns.

Figure 5: Heart rate sensor Polar Verity Scene in dripping device (Provided by Chun-Huang LIN).

- **Dripping Control:** After testing three methods including Solenoid valve, peristaltic pump, and electronic drip titration, electronic drip titration was selected. This decision was made due to the difficulty in controlling the precise dripping of one drop at a time and stability issues with Solenoid valve and peristaltic pumping. Electronic drip titration uses a stepper motor combined with a screw mechanism, allowing for precise control and subtle variations in dripping rate by tight up the tubing. By employing Proportional Integral Control (PI control) and monitoring with an optocoupler speed sensor, the error in dripping is controlled within 0.1 seconds.
- **Water Reservoir:** Above the device, there is a water storage serving as the water source needed during the experience. Considering hygiene concerns, the water source is not recycled, and re-filled through periodic manual. Additionally, another water storage space is designed below the device, allowing most of the water to flow in through holes to avoid splashing.

Figure 6: Electronic drip titration in dripping device (Provided by Chun-Huang LIN).

- **Virtual Reality:** The VR utilizes the Oculus Quest 2 head-mounted display and the Unity game engine for creation and presentation. The integration between the visuals and the dripping device is achieved through wireless socket communication, with a server to ensure consistency in interactions between the device and visuals. This enables synchronous interactive experiences across visual, auditory, and tactile senses.

6 Phase One: Art Exhibition

First phase of “Time Organ” is explored the issue of human detachment from bodily time in an artistic form. The exhibition took place from April 11th to 14th, 2024, at Laval Virtual – Recto VRso – The Art & VR Gallery (Le Quarante, Laval, France). Each experience is

Figure 7: Schematic explanation diagram of interconnection mechanism and control component technology (Provided by Chi-Hung HUANG).

approximately seven minutes, and it is estimated that about 150 experiencers engaged in the experience during the exhibition. Below are some summaries record of observations during the experience and feedback from experiencers:

6.1 Observations

- (1) During the experience, the heart rate of most experiencers gradually decreased with reduced fluctuations. This could be cause by the overall slow pace of the experience or the continuous presence of slower visual, auditory, and tactile frequencies.
- (2) Experiencers exhibited a noticeable increase in heart rate when the water first dripped. Most experiencers responded to this with surprise or excitement upon feeling the water for the first time.
- (3) Due to the heart rate sensor not being directly worn by the experiencers, there were occasional instances during the experience where the signal was interrupted due to the arm not contacting the sensor.

6.2 Experiencer Feedback

After experiencing the installation, most experiencers provided that the topic of the artwork was unique, and the overall form presented a rare tactile experience. The synchronization of the tactile and visual sensations of dripping water was particularly impressive. As previously observed, most participants felt calmer after the experience. Additionally, because the heart rate sensor was concealed within the installation platform rather than worn directly, some participants were initially unaware that their heart rate was being monitored in real time. These participants noted that they sensed changes in the dripping frequency, which were not associated with quantified time. Below are some of the more distinctive feedback comments we received:

- (1) Using “heartbeats” instead of “heart rate” for body detection would better align with the intended content.

- (2) Water temperature could serve as another variable element, allowing for a more diverse sensory experience.
- (3) Presenting the visual imagery in grayscale helps focus more on the tactile sensations beyond vision.
- (4) The appearance easily evokes associations with medical equipment or some form of sculpture, with experiencers themselves becoming part of the sculpture.

Based on the feedback, we discovered many details in the experience process that could help the audience immerse themselves in the context and enhance the tactile sensations, such as visual style and device design. Future iterations of the artwork will further incorporate these suggestions for improvement.

Figure 8: “Time Organ” at the Laval Virtual – Recto VRso exhibition venue. Exhibition video documentation: <https://youtu.be/wNNJ75p24HY?si=SQ663QuFaD6RJgkm> (Provided by Chun-Huang LIN).

7 Future

“Time Organ” project explores the issue of human insensitivity to bodily time through art, guiding time frequencies towards bodily frequencies under active control. After an exhibition, feedback from experiencers will be analyzed to optimize the experience. In the next phase, the project aims to experiment whether Synchronization can prompt individuals to perceive time with bodily rhythms. The experimental design will again use a dripping device to amplify the sense of heart rate, reducing guiding elements in visual and auditory to balance various sensory stimuli. Additionally, more body sensors such as heart rate monitors, EEGs, and eye trackers will be used to monitor changes in experiencers’ bodily frequencies. The entire study will also utilize qualitative research methods to collect more feedback from participants, aiming to gain a deeper understanding of each experiencers’ bodily sensations through in-depth interviews.

8 Conclusion

With the evolution of timekeeping tools, the division of time units has become increasingly refined and precise. From the earliest mechanical water clocks to modern atomic clocks, the pursuit of more precise time measurement has been relentless. However, this extreme precision in quantified time often far from our most direct bodily experiences of time, leading to an increasing insensibility of the passage of time. “Time Organ” art project tries to explore this issue of detachment from bodily time. Based on the instinct of human synchronicity, the project tries to guide our understanding of time back to our own bodily frequency through multi-sensory asynchronous and synchronous experiences. Through the combination of virtual reality and a custom-made dripping device with heart rate sensor, the project creates an experience that visual and tactile senses shift from asynchronous to synchronous. In addition to presenting this exploration through artistic creation, future efforts will focus on using qualitative research to experiment with whether Synchronization can prompt individuals to perceive time with bodily rhythms. The goal is to further research and find the different solutions for the issue of detachment from bodily time.

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